

NON-DESTRUCTIVE INSPECTION OF CFRPS USING INDUCTION HEATING THERMOGRAPHY

Y. Shiiya^{1*}, M. Ishikawa¹, Y. Kogo¹, H. Hatta² and Y. Habuka³

¹ Tokyo University of Science, Tokyo, Japan,

² Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency, Kanagawa, Japan,

³ KJTD, Co., Ltd., Tokyo, Japan,

* Corresponding author (uk1.1224@gmail.com)

Keywords: CFRP, Non-destructive inspection, Thermography, FEM

1 Introduction

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRPs) are often used as structural material in aircrafts and automobiles in recent years. With the increase of use of CFRPs, more effective and convenient non-destructive inspection (NDI) methods are also required. In the NDI techniques, pulse phase thermography (PPT) [1] is one of a non-contact and a convenient method. The schematic views of the PPT method are showed in Fig. 1. In PPT, temperature data of object surface after applying instantaneous pulse heating are obtained by an infrared camera, and the temperature data are Fourier transformed to phase data. Previous paper reported that deeper defects were detected in phase images constructed using the phase data, and that the detectable depths of defects with 10 mm in diameter in a CFRP laminate were 5-6 mm [2]. Additionally, in the phase images, reduction of non-uniform heating was also reported. However, because thermal conductivity of CFRPs in out-of-plane direction is small, larger inspection time is required to detect deeper defects when heating from the object surface.

In order to shorten the testing time for CFRPs, present study focused on using induction heating thermography (IHT) [3,4]. In this method, because objects were heated from inside, inspection time should be half of the required time for the conventional method. This study aims to detect delamination defects in CFRP laminates using IHT. As first step to this aim, flat-bottomed defects were assumed as artificial defects in this paper, and the temperature and phase data obtained by using IHT were evaluated by experiments and analyses based on finite element method (FEM).

Fig. 1 Schematic illustration of the pulse phase thermography method.

2 Experiments by using IHT method

2.1 Principle of induction heating

Principle of the induction heating thermography is schematically shown in Fig. 2. In IHT, an induction coil is positioned near the test object, and Joule heat generated due to induced eddy current in CFRP is utilized as heat source. Because CFRPs are heated from inside, time for detecting defects should be smaller than the conventional thermography methods. In addition, by transforming the temperature data obtained by IHT to phase data, detectable defect depth should be also improved. However, it is concerned in the IHT that non-uniform heating due to the shape of induction coil and fiber orientation in CFRPs significantly affects the defect detectability.

Fig. 2 Schematic views of induction heating thermography method.

Fig. 3 CFRP specimen with flat-bottomed holes defects (a), and with flat-bottomed grooves (b). Numerals in the pictures show the defect depth from the surface.

2.2 Fourier transformation for evaluation of phase images

The obtained temperature data were transformed to phase data by applying Fourier transform. By using the real and imaginary parts of the complex data obtained after Fourier transforming, and phase data ($\varphi(f)$) for constructing phase image are calculated using the equation below.

$$\varphi(f) = \tan^{-1} \frac{I(f)}{R(f)} \quad (1)$$

where f is the frequency, and $R(f)$ and $I(f)$ stand for the real and imaginary parts of the transform, respectively. Then, the phase images are constructed using the $\varphi(f)$. In the phase images, inside defects were detected by detecting phase difference between defective and non-defective areas ($\Delta\varphi$). The $\Delta\varphi$ attributes the temperature difference before Fourier transform. The frequency range of the phase data depends of the sampling frequency of infrared camera (f_s) and the number of data (n).

Fig. 4 Experimental set-up for induction heating thermography.

The maximum frequency (f_{max}) and the minimum frequency (f_{min}) are determined as follows.

$$f_{max} = f_s/2 \quad (2)$$

$$f_{min} = f_s/n \quad (3)$$

2.3 Experimental setup

Two CFRP specimens reinforced with PAN based carbon fibers (T300 and T800, Toray Co. Ltd.) were used in the experiments. One has ten flat-bottomed holes (Fig.3(a)), and another has twelve flat-bottomed grooves (Fig.3(b)) as artificial defects. The thickness of the specimens was respectively 4 and 5 mm, and the depths of defects; t are presented in Fig. 3. Experimental set-up was shown in Fig. 4. In the experiments, an induction coil made of litz wire (coil diameter was 140 mm, wire diameter was 2.4 mm) was positioned under the specimen. By using bipolar DC power supply (BP4610, NF Corporation), alternating current with 25.3 A, 92 V and frequency of 10 kHz were applied to the coil. The temperature distribution on the surface of the specimen during heating (480 s) and after stop heating (120 s) was monitored by an infrared camera (A315, FLIR Systems Inc.). The sampling rate of the IR camera was 3.75 Hz. Then the obtained temperature images were transformed to phase images by image analysis software (IR Phaser10, KJTD Co., Ltd. [5]).

Fig. 5 Temperature images for the specimen with flat-bottomed holes, (a) at 53 s (during heating), (b) at 480 s (after heating) and (c) at 600 s (after cooling).

2.4 Experimental results

2.4.1 Flat-bottomed hole specimen

Obtained temperature images of the specimen with flat-bottomed holes were showed in Fig. 5. In the temperature image, defects with depth of 0.2 and 0.4 mm ($\phi 10$ mm) were detected as cooler spots than the non-defective area. However, it was difficult to detect other defects. This is because non-uniform heating due to the shape of the induction coil disturbs the detection of defects. On the other hand, in the phase image (Fig. 6), though the effects of non-uniform heating was observed in low frequency range (Fig. 6(a)), its effect is reduced with increasing frequency. In the phase images at higher frequency than 0.04 Hz (Fig. 6 (c), (d)), the defects with defect depth of 0.6, 0.8 and 1.0 mm ($\phi 10$ mm), 0.2 and 0.4 mm ($\phi 5$ mm) were detected.

2.4.2 Flat-bottomed groove specimen

Experimental results for the specimen with flat-bottomed grooves are showed in Fig. 7. The flat-bottomed groove defects are assumed as the crack

Fig. 6 Phase images at the frequency of (a) 0.0167 Hz, (b) 0.0200 Hz, (c) 0.0433 Hz, (d) 0.0517 Hz.

defects. If the cracks disturb the flow of the current, the current circumvents the defects, and current concentration is occurred at the edge of the crack. It is reported that the edges of defect appear as locally hotter spot than the sound area [6,7]. However, in the experimentally obtained temperature image as seen in Fig. 7(a), such local temperature difference could not be observed. On the other hand, in the phase images shown in Fig. 7 (b), the edges of defect with the defect depth 1.0 and 2.0 mm were detected owing to reduction of the influence of non-uniform heating. In addition, the phase image at lower frequency (Fig. 7(c)), the defects with the defect depth of 0.5 and 1.0 mm are clearly detected. These results suggest that using the phase images is effective to reduce the influence of the non-uniform heating caused by the shape of the coil, and that this lead to improvement of the defect detectability.

2.4.3 Discussions for the experimental results

Though the defects were detected as local cold area in the temperature images for the flat-bottomed hole specimen, those were detected as local hot spots for the flat-bottomed groove specimen. By

Fig. 7 The results of flat-bottomed groove specimen. (a) temperature image at 480 s, and the phase images (b) at 0.0133 Hz and (c) at 0.0167 Hz.

comparing these results, required time to detect local hot area due to concentration of current defects is shorter. Therefore, detecting such inhomogeneous temperature spots is effective to shorten the inspection time.

3 FEM Analyses

In order to evaluate the current flow and temperature distribution in the CFRP specimens, finite element analyses were performed. In this study, the commercial FEM software ANSYS ver. 13.0 (ANSYS Inc.) was used.

3.1 FEM models

The analytical model is represented in Fig. 8. Due to symmetric shape, 1/4 models were used. The model size and material properties of each component are shown in Table 1 and 2, respectively. The size of the induction coil and CFRP specimen are the same conditions as the experiment, and the defect depth are varied from 0.5 mm to 3 mm as

Fig. 8 3D model used in the analyses (lower figure shows the cross-sectional view of the upper model).

shown in Table 1. The analyses were magnetic-heat transfer analysis. In magnetic analyses, alternating current of 92 V with frequency of 10 kHz was applied to the coil, and Joule heat generation induced in CFRP was calculated. In the heat transfer analyses, temperature distribution caused by the Joule heat generation calculated by the magnetic analyses was obtained. The initial temperature for the model was 20 °C. From the calculated result, the temperature at the node of the defect (as showed in Fig. 8) is obtained. In addition, to obtain the temperature data on non-defective area, analysis for the model without defect was also performed.

3.2 Analytical results and discussion

3.2.1 Comparison between analytical and experimental results

In order to compare the FEM results with the results of the experiment for flat-bottomed hole defects, surface temperatures on the specimen were calculated in same condition with the experiment (heating duration was 480 s, and time after stop heating was 120 s). The temperature history on

Table 1 Detail of the geometry of the components used in the analyses.

Component		[mm]
Size		75×75×4
CFRP specimen	Defect diameter	10
	Defect depth	0.5, 1.0, 2.0, 3.0
Coil	Outer radius	71
	Inner radius	20.6
	Wire diameter	2.4

Table 2 Material properties used in the analyses.

	CFRP	Coil
Permeability	1	1
Electrical resistivity [$\Omega \cdot m$]	In-plane ; 1.46×10^{-4}	1.0×10^{-8}
	Out-of-plane ; 1.46×10^{-1}	
Thermal conductivity [W/m · K]	In-plane ; 6	-
	Out-of-plane ; 0.48	
Density[kg/m ³]	1600	-
Specific heat[J/kg · K]	1530	-

defective and non-defective are shown in Fig. 9. In the results, the temperature of the defect area after 480 s is cooler than the non-defect area. This is the same tendency with the observed temperature images obtained by experiments.

3.2.2 The temperature distribution of flat-bottomed hole specimen

Figure 10 shows the eddy current distribution around the defect with depth of 1 mm calculated by the magnetic analysis. The current concentration was obtained. This result suggests that there is a possibility to detect the flat-bottomed hole defects by detecting heat concentration. Figure 11 shows the temperature difference between obtained on the local hot spots and on non-defective area for various depths of defects. It is found from this figure that, with increasing the defect depth, the maximum value of the temperature difference (ΔT_{max}) decreases and the time at ΔT_{max} (t_{max}) increases. However,

Fig. 9 The temperature history calculated on defective and non-defective area.

Fig. 10 Calculated eddy current distribution around the defect with depth of 1 mm.

Fig. 11 Temperature difference between defective and non-defective area for each depth of defects.

because the temperature difference is very small for each depth of defects, the heat concentration is undetected in the experiment.

3.2.3 Calculation of phase data

In order to detect very small the heating concentration in flat-bottomed hole defect, the temperature data obtained in the analyses were transformed to the phase data by applying FFT. FFT was applied only on the temperature data obtained after stop heating. In addition, in order to examine S/N (signal to noise) ratio for phase data, noise simulate temperature data with temperature noise observed in IR cameras, the random numbers following the normal distribution (the standard variation was 0.065 °C) were added to the temperature data calculated by the analysis. Then, by applying FFT to the noise-including temperature data, phase data with noise were obtained. The phase noise are calculated for each frequency by using 10 different random numbers, and the peak-to-peak value of the phase noise for each frequency is calculated.

Calculated phase difference between defective and non-defective area is showed in Fig. 12. This figure shows that the maximum phase difference ($\Delta\phi_{max}$) and the frequency at $\Delta\phi_{max}$ is decreased with

Fig. 12 Phase differences between defective and non-defective area for each depth of defects.

Fig. 13 Comparison of S/N ratios for the temperature and phase data for each depth of defects.

increasing defect depth. Figure 13 shows the S/N ratios for each depth of defects. In this figure, S/N ratios for temperature data were also presented for comparison. Because ΔT_{max} is decreased with increasing defect depth is, the S/N ratio for the temperature data is decreased with increasing defect depth. The S/N ratios for the phase data are approximately the same with those for the

Fig. 14 Analytically simulated phase noise distribution as a function of frequency for defect with depth of 1 mm.

temperature data, and are almost smaller than 1. These results imply that the ΔT_{max} and $\Delta \phi_{max}$ are too small to detect.

3.2.4 Exploration of inspection condition to detect the ΔT_{max} and $\Delta \phi_{max}$

In order to investigate conditions to detect the ΔT_{max} and $\Delta \phi_{max}$, another analyses were carried out with varying the input voltage. Figure 14 represents the calculated phase noise as a function of frequency when input voltage were 92, 166 and 263 V. Though the $\Delta \phi_{max}$ is constant regardless of the input voltage, the phase noise is decreased with increasing the input voltage. The reduction of the phase noise leads to improvement of S/N ratio for phase data.

Required input voltage to achieve temperature difference of 0.2 and 0.5 °C for defects with each depth estimated by the analyses are presented in Table 3. On the basis of these results, S/N ratios for temperature and phase data when the temperature difference is 0.2 and 0.5 °C are presented in Fig.15. This figure shows that the S/N ratio for the phase data is larger than that for temperature data. In addition, all the S/N ratio for the phase data are larger than 1. These results clearly suggest that using

Table 3 Required voltages to achieve $\Delta T_{max} = 0.2, 0.5$ °C for each depth of defects.

Defect depth / mm	The input voltage / V	
	at $\Delta T_{max} = 0.2$ °C	at $\Delta T_{max} = 0.5$ °C
0.5	161	254
1	166	263
2	198	313
3	232	367

Fig. 15 Comparison of S/N ratios for the temperature and the phase data for each depth of defects when $\Delta T_{max} = 0.2, 0.5$ °C.

phase data are more effective to detect local hot spot around the defects occurred due to the concentration of current flow than temperature images.

4 Conclusions

As Non-destructive inspection technique for CFRPs, the phase data obtained by using induction heating thermography are evaluated. The main findings obtained by the experiment and the analyses using FEM are shown as followed;

1. The flat-bottomed hole defects were detected as lower temperature region than the non-defective area. On the other hand, for the flat-bottomed groove defects, the current concentration were observed, and the edge of the defects were detected as local hot spots. In the phase images obtained after applying Fourier transform to the temperature images, the non-uniform heating was reduces and the defect detectability was improved.
2. The analytical results showed that current concentration was also occurred around the flat-bottomed hole defects, and detecting such local hot spot should be lead to shorten the inspection time.
3. The S/N ratio for the phase data are larger than that for temperature data. This results means using phase data is more effective to detect defects.

References

- [1] X. Maldague and S. Marinetti “Pulse phase infrared thermography”. *J. Appl. Phys.* 79, pp.2694-2698, 1996.
- [2] M. Ishikawa, H. Hatta, Y. Habuka, S. Jinnai and S. Ustunomiya “Effect of Anisotropic Properties on Defect Detection by Pulse Phase Thermography”. *Advanced Composite Materials*, 21, pp.67-78, 2012.
- [3] T. Salagami, S. Kubo, “Development of a New crack Identification Technique Based on Near-Tip Singular Electrothermal Field Measured by Lock-in Infrared Thermography”. *JSME International journal Series A*, 44(4), pp.528-534, 2001.
- [4] M. Pan, Y. He, G. Tian, D. Chen, F. Luo, “Defect characterization using pulsed eddy current thermography under transmission mode and NDT applications”. *NDT&E International*, 52, pp.28-36, 2012.
- [5] KJTD Co. Ltd.
<http://www.kjtd.co.jp/products/thermo_inspector/index.html>
- [6] T. Salagami, K. Ougura, “A New Flaw Inspection Technic Based on Infrared Thermal Images Under Joule Effect Heating”. *JSME International journal Series A*, 58(555), pp.2224-2231, 1992
- [7] K. Moriya, “A study on Flaw Detection Method for CFRP Composite Laminates (2nd Report) Use of Joule Effect for Detecting Flaws and Local Fiber Concentrations in CFRP Composites”. *The Journal of the Japan Society of Aeronautical Engineering*, 37(424), pp.238-246, 1989.